

A Study of the Complexes of the so-called Ethereal Blue Peroxychromic Acid with Dimethyl Aniline and *o*-Amino Phenol

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Manuscript received 15 February 1972; revised 13 September 1972; accepted 25 January 1973

Different samples of dimethyl aniline and *o*-amino phenol complexes with blue peroxychromic acid have been prepared and analysed. The chemical behaviour and the paramagnetic nature of the complexes suggest that the ethereal blue compound contains trivalent chromium along with hexavalent chromium and is chromium peroxychromate.

SCHWARZ and Giese¹ assigned the formula, PyCrO_3 for pyridine complex using Wiede's method². Rai³ and his co-workers⁴ prepared pyridine, piperidine, quinoline, 8-hydroxy quinoline and strychnine complexes of the so-called ethereal blue peroxychromic acid, following Wiede's method (loc. cit.) and suggested the presence of trivalent chromium along with hexavalent chromium in them, Rajput, Govil and Singhal⁵ supported the view of Rai. In view of conflicting reports of earlier workers, it was considered worthwhile to study the nature of the complexes formed from blue perchromate with dimethyl aniline and *o*-amino phenol for which there is no indication in the literature.

Experimental

The ethereal blue peroxychromic acid was prepared as described by Rai³. The chemicals used were 5% (W/V) potassium dichromate (50 ml.), 2*N*-sulphuric acid (50 ml.), 6% hydrogen peroxide (25 ml.) and ether (400 ml.).

Dimethyl aniline complex: An excess of dimethyl aniline (double distilled) was added to the ethereal blue perchromate (150 ml.). The greenish black complex was obtained in about 10 hr. The precipitate thus obtained was filtered and washed with ether several times till the filtrate was colourless. It was then dried in a desiccator.

O-Amino phenol complex: A dark brown complex was readily obtained after the addition of ethereal solution of *o*-amino phenol (10%) in slight excess to the ethereal blue compound (150 ml.). It was filtered and dried in the same way as in the case of dimethyl aniline complex.

Estimation of total chromium: The complex on heating decomposed to a green product of Cr_2O_3 . Thus definite weights of the two complexes were

taken separately in previously weighed silica crucibles and heated at first gently and then strongly. After complete ignition, these were cooled, weighed as Cr_2O_3 and from this, the percentage of total chromium was calculated.

Oxidising powers of the two complexes in sodium hydroxide solution: The oxidising powers of the complexes were determined by iodometric titrations. Definite weights of the two complexes were separately dissolved in 200 ml. of *N*-sodium hydroxide and each was made up to 250 ml. Dimethyl aniline was not found to be completely soluble in sodium hydroxide, therefore its solution had to be warmed.

25 ml. of each of the two solutions was taken, added to aqueous solution of potassium iodide and acidified with dilute sulphuric acid till distinctly acidic. The liberated iodine was titrated against the standard solution of sodium thiosulphate using starch as an indicator.

Estimation of chromium in the basic part: Estimation of chromium in the basic part of the complexes was carried out by employing the two methods:

(i) *Volumetric method*: 25 ml. aliquots were separately taken in conical flasks and were oxidised by adding 5 ml. of 30% hydrogen peroxide. The excess of peroxide was removed by prolonged boiling. After complete oxidation, the contents of the flasks were cooled to room temperature, acidified with 2*N*-sulphuric acid and titrated iodometrically with the same sodium thiosulphate solution.

(ii) *Gravimetric method*: 25 ml. aliquots were separately taken in pyrex beakers which were kept on water bath. Heating was continued till green chromium hydroxide was completely precipitated. The precipitate was filtered through gravimetric filter paper and washed with hot water till free from sodium hydroxide and chromate ions. It was then dried, ignited and weighed as Cr_2O_3 . This gave the amount of chromium present in the basic part of the complex.

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Oxidising power of the filtrate: The filtrates obtained from the above gravimetric method were separately taken along with their washings acidified with 2*N*-sulphuric acid till distinctly acidic and titrated iodometrically against the same sodium thio-sulphate solution.

Estimation of nitrogen, carbon and hydrogen of the two complexes: Complexes were also analysed for N, C and H.

Magnetic measurements: Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out using Gouy's balance at room temperature viz., 27°.

Discussion

It is evident from the table 1 that the titre values of column 'b' are the same as those of column 'd' (vide ratio *d/b*). It corresponds to the amount of chromium the acidic part of the complex. The increase in the titre value after oxidation indicates that the complex may contain trivalent chromium along with hexavalent chromium. From the table it is also evident that the titre values of column 'c' are the double to those of column 'b' or 'd' (vide ratios *c/b*, *c/d*). This clearly shows that chromium is present in the acidic as well as in the basic part of the complexes in equal proportions. This view is further confirmed from the fact that the percentage of total chromium is double that of chromium obtained in the basic part of the complex (vide column *j*).

alkali solution forming chromate. Keeping in view the above data and the chemical properties of these complexes, the molecular formula for dimethyl aniline complex may be represented as $R_2Cr(CrO_{10})$, $R_4Cr_2(Cr_2O_{20})$ or $R_4Cr_2(CrO_{10})_2$ and for *o*-amino phenol complex as $R_3Cr(CrO_{10})$.

The magnetic moment for dimethyl aniline complex is found to 3.987 B.M. for *o*-amino phenol 4.062 B.M. The two complexes are found to be paramagnetic in nature and magnetic moment of the complexes is consistent with the presence of the three unpaired electrons further supporting the presence of trivalent chromium in them.

It is clear from the experimental analysis of the above two complexes that these consist of the same amount of chromium in the acidic as well as in the basic parts. Thus, from the proposed molecular formulae and magnetic susceptibility for these two complexes, it can be concluded that the so-called blue peroxychromic acid contains trivalent chromium along with hexavalent chromium and is really chromium peroxychromate.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Dr. W. U. Malik, Professor and Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, Roorkee for providing necessary facilities to take magnetic measurements in the department.

TABLE 1

(x) 0.1174 g of dimethyl aniline complex dissolved in 250 ml. of *N*-NaOH.
(x) 0.1144 g of *o*-amino phenol complex dissolved in 250 ml. of *N*-NaOH.
Volume of hypo soln. used in titrating (25 ml of x)

Complex	Soln. (x) before oxidation	Soln. (x) after oxidation	Filtrate of Cr(OH) ₃ pptn. from soln. (x)	After pptn. Cr(OH) ₃ from (d) % of Cr in basic part (method ii)	Percentage of total Cr.	Ratios			
						<i>c/b</i>	<i>c/d</i>	<i>d/b</i>	<i>f/e</i>
(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)	(f)	(g)	(h)	(i)	(j)
1. Dimethyl aniline	6.60	13.50	6.65	10.10	20.30	2.04	2.03	1.01	2.01
	6.60	13.50	6.70	10.15	20.30	2.04	2.01	1.01	2.00
2. <i>o</i> -amino phenol	5.35	11.10	5.45	8.60	16.99	2.07	2.03	1.01	1.97
	5.40	11.15	5.45	8.65	17.05	2.05	2.04	1.01	1.97

TABLE 2

Percentage of elements

Complex	Proposed formula	Cr		N		H		C	
		Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
1. Dimethyl aniline.	$R_2Cr(CrO_{10})$	20.55	20.30	5.53	5.76	4.35	4.50	37.94	38.80
2. <i>o</i> -amino phenol.	$R_3Cr(CrO_{10})$	17.59	17.05	7.10	6.89	3.55	3.50	36.55	35.72

From the Tables 1 and 2, it is concluded that the empirical formula for dimethyl aniline complex is found to be $RCrO_5$ and for *o*-amino phenol complex $R_{1.5}CrO_5$ or $R_3Cr_2O_{10}$, where R stands for one molecule of organic bases. The molecular weight of these complexes cannot be determined due to their insolubility in almost all solvents. These begin to decompose soon after dissolution if at all takes place in any of the solvents. These are soluble in

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